

ອາລະສານວິຊາການ

ອັກສອນສາດລາວ

ເວທີສຳເລັມການສຶກສາຄົ້ນຄວ້າ ແລະເພີຍແພ່ພົນການຄົ້ນຄວ້າ, ຫຼັກການ
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DEPARTMENT OF LAO LANGUAGE AND CULTURE
CENTER FOR RESEARCH IN LAO LANGUAGES
FACULTY OF LETTERS
NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF LAOS
DONGDOK CAMPUS

ນະຫວີທະຍາໄລແຫ່ງຊາດ
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ອັກສອນສາດລາວ

ສະບັບປະຈຳປີທີ 3 ພສ 2564 ຄສ 2021

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Rhyme over reason: Language, counting and play in Northern Laos

Nathan Badenoch
Department of Global Interdisciplinary Studies
Villanova University

1. Introduction

The reconstruction of Austroasiatic numerals has presented interesting challenges to our understanding of the history of these languages and their speakers (Diffloth and Zide 1975; Sidwell 1999; Rischel 2009)¹². Numeral systems have been reconstructed for all branches of the family, but there is still a large degree of internal inconsistency and historical instability. It seems that numerals ‘one’ to ‘four’ have a solid history (Sidwell 1999), but beyond that questions remain. Thomas (1976) asked early on whether counting beyond four or five was common in the proto language. Moreover, it is not clear whether the protolanguage had a decimal system (Sidwell 2012).

Not surprisingly, many of these questions are problems related to the cultural practices of counting of the speakers (Rischel 1997). Typologically, the study of numeral systems is complicated because of the mathematical principles that underpin the structuring of the incremental steps, and the cycle of repetition needed to reproduce the system. There is also the possibility that counting and quantifying are done not only through the use of “numerals,” but other classes of words. Furthermore, one must remember that numeral systems are used for a number of functions. Most commonly encountered is the distinction between cardinal and ordinal numerals, but other functions can include recitation and counting out loud, in ritual or play situations. These concerns have resonated within research on the languages affiliated with the Khmuic branch, because of widespread replacement of the lower numerals with Tai forms.

This paper starts with the assumption that a language may have more than one way of counting, quantifying and using numerical progressions in society. I start my exploration from Bit, an Austroasiatic language spoken in Luang Namtha province, northwestern Laos. Native numerals for counting and most functions of quantification have been replaced with borrowings from Tai. However, there are sets of terms that are used by children in play that represent another sociolinguistic realm of counting. I was surprised when I encountered a similar set of play numerals in the Phong Laan language, a language spoken in Houaphan province, adjacent to Vietnam in northeastern Laos. The presence of a play counting system would not necessarily be surprising, as they are found around the globe, but the formal and functional similarities between the Bit and Phong Laan play counting sets were striking.

Exploring various ways of counting in the Austroasiatic languages spoken in northern Laos reveals a rich diversity of counting systems that exhibit a wide range of functions, as well as a strong sense of poetic creativity. It seems that the shared inheritance of numerals from proto-Austroasiatic is intertwined with strong forces of innovation driven by local preferences for word play, periods of language contact and shifting power balances among local groups in the area. The data on Bit are supplemented by my own field data from Ksingmul and Phong, as well as published and data from the Mal-Pray and Mlabri languages (Rischel 2009). I pick up on observations and analysis offered by the Danish linguist Jørgen Rischel, who encouraged linguists to work outside the standard lexicon and explore more specialized areas of linguistic practice, such as ritual, folklore and play, in search of insights into the history of these languages and the people that speak them. His work on Austroasiatic numerals, based on his own field

¹² For a comparative view of Austroasiatic numerals, see Sidwell (2012) “Austroasiatic Numerals”, data presented at the 22nd Annual Meeting of the Southeast Asian Linguistics Society; <https://sites.google.com/view/paulsidwell/austroasiatic-numerals?authuser=0>.

and theoretical work, opened up a linguistic perspective on numeral systems that asks us to look broadly at counting as culture.

In the analysis of Bit, the aesthetic features of rhyming, reduplication and rhythm are central to the maintenance of the play counting series, where the meaning of the words has long been lost for those who recite them. Yet, because they seem to preserve elements of the old numerals, and because other related languages have similar systems, they show how play can result in both innovation and retention of linguistic features. Ways of playful counting can be considered part of an areal phenomenon among some Austroasiatic groups in Northern Laos. These practices, playing out at the interface of performance and poetics, deepen our understanding the loss of native numerals in languages in contact with Tai languages.

2. Loss of numerals as a regional phenomenon

Within the Austroasiatic languages spoken in the upland areas of Laos, it is common to find that native numerals have been replaced with Tai borrowings, either partially or completely¹³. The loss of numerals has considered to be part of the consequences of intense contact with Tai languages in this area. For example, most varieties of Khmu retain Austroasiatic numerals one to three (*mooy*, *baar*, *peʔ*) but use Tai for four and above. The historical depth of this borrowing is indicated by the retention of /r/, now shifted to /h/ in all SW Tai languages except Siamese, in ‘six’ *rok* and ‘hundred’ *rɔɔy*. At the outset of this discussion, it is worth recalling that borrowing of numerals has been a frequent occurrence historically in the region. For example, numerals in Southwestern Tai languages such as Thai, Lao and Tai Dam, are all borrowings from Sino-Tibetan, with the exception of *nij* ‘one’ and *saw* ‘twenty’. The social dynamics behind the borrowing of numeral systems is not well understood in these cases. Moreover, the linguistic processes through which these changes took place are not known.

One finds a situation similar to Khmu in Phong and Ksingmul, both spoken in Houaphan province. The details vary by language and variety. The retention of low numerals one to three is part of a practice in which counting as recitation is done with borrowed Tai forms, but the remaining native terms are used in conjunction with noun classifiers for quantification. For example, speakers of Phong will recite borrowed Tai numerals *nij sɔɔŋ saam* but use native ‘one’ to ‘three’ when used with classifiers; for example *baʔan*, *baarʔan*, *peʔan*, where *ʔan* is the general noun classifier borrowed from Tai. In Ksingmul, similarly, one may hear *met khon*, *biar khon*, *peɛ khon*, with *khon* ‘person.’ Selection of numerals in a hybrid system depends upon the usage.

Bit is further along the transformation to a Tai-based numeral system. Bit uses the Tai numerals for almost all normal counting and quantification done in daily speech (Table 1).

Table 1: “Normal” Bit cardinal numerals, borrowed from Tai

1	nij	6	hok
2	sɔɔŋ	7	cet
3	saam	8	peɛt
4	sii	9	kaw
5	haa	10	sip

Unlike Khmu, ‘six’ is not pronounced with the historical /r/ although Bit does typically retain historical /r/ in many words of Tai origin. The /r/ pronunciation may be used for effect, but Bit speakers generally associate this with Khmu. The /r/ is however preserved in ‘100’ *rɔɔy* when occurring in compound terms such as the military rank *naay rɔɔy*, literally ‘commander of 100’,

¹³ This is observed in the Aslian languages of Malaysia as well (Diffloth 1976).

a title for labor brokers. As will be discussed more below, native forms for ‘one’ and ‘two’ are still found in the language, but in specialized usage.

3. Linguistic diversity, reconstructing Khmuic and shifting the numeral focus

Despite the frequent loss of numerals, native systems are found intact throughout the area as well. Khmu had previously been taken as an important point of reference because it was the best described Austroasiatic language in the area. The concern for Khmuic counting was first concerned with the replacement of higher numerals under pressure from linguistic contact with Tai languages. However, with more data, starting with a full set of native Khmu numerals found in Thailand, a different picture of Khmuic numerals emerged. A growing awareness of these, based on the social networks of Khmu elders in Vientiane, has led announcers in the Lao National Radio Khmu section to experiment with integrating native Austroasiatic numerals in efforts to re-localize the language, which has a high level of specialized lexical borrowing from Lao in official broadcasts (Badenoch 2018). Because these numbers have not been used in villages, it is not clear how widely they are understood, and there has not been a revival of these numerals in Khmu spoken in Laos.

Now a full set of numerals one to ten is known for Mlabri, Thai Then, Iduh, and Mal-Pray, and the Palaungic language Lamet (Table 2), all spoken in Northern Laos.

Table 2: Numerals 1-10 in Austroasiatic languages spoken in Northern Laos

	Khmu (Rischel 2009)	Mlabri (Rischel 1995)	Thai Then (Diffloth, p.c.)	Iduh (Diffloth p.c.)	T'in (Rischel 2009)	Lamet (Sidwell 2012)
1	mooy	məːj	moy	hndiːy	muːj	mooh
2	baar	bɛːr	beer	hmbaːʔr	pia	ʔlaːr
3	pɛʔ	pɛʔ	pɛʔ	mpey ^h	pheʔ	ʔlɔːj
4	phuan	pon	pon	mpɔn	phoːn	poːn
5	phian	thɔːŋ	siŋ	hnsɔŋ	sɔːŋ	phan
6	tɔl	taːl	tɔːl	hntul	thuːl	tɔːl
7	guul	gul	gul	krɔgul	ŋgul	puːl
8	tiʔ	tiːʔ	rɔŋ	kəruuŋʔ	thiʔ	taʔ
9	khay	gaɻ	tiʔ	gntey	ŋgat	tiːm
10	kal	gal	gal	məgoaʔa	matuk / tuk	keːl

It is worth pointing out that the Iduh numerals are all disyllabic, an important feature of the play counting systems discussed here. These are formed by the addition of a minor syllable before the base form. The Thai Then set collected by Souksavang in 1992 (referenced in Rischel 2009) also has sesquisyllabic forms, some of which are the result of infixing and consonant mutation: *mooy*, *ndɛɛr*, *pdeʔ*, *ndɔŋ*, *suŋ*, *tɔl*, *gul*, *roŋ*, *tiʔ*, *mkaɻ*. The infixing of /d/ is peculiar, and it is worth noting the /ŋ/ final of ‘four’, which would historically be /n/.

This new data has enabled a reconstruction of proto-Khmuic numerals (Sidwell 2012), shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Proto-Khmuic Numerals

1	*moːj	6	*tVl
2	*baːr	7	*guːl
3	*peʔ	8	*taːm / *tiʔ
4	*puəŋ	9	*kaːj / *kaːs
5	*səːŋ	10	*gal

There is some variation in the numerals ‘eight’, ‘nine’ and ‘ten’, which is in line with the larger tendency towards instability in the higher numerals across the Austroasiatic world.

While the reconstruction of Khmuic numerals is an important development for the history of Austroasiatic, the research that produced this data raised other questions about language and counting. The discovery of alternative systems for counting bring up numerous questions about the nature of quantification, use of poetic rhythm and semantic fluidity (Rischel 2009). This brings to the forefront the social life of numerals in the multiethnic, dynamic landscapes of the uplands.

4. One, two and the other

In Bit, recitation numerals have all been replaced with the Thai forms. In 1892, when Lefevre-Pontalis collected a short list of words from the Bit in Laos and Vietnam, this replacement had already happened. However, in the Bit currently spoken in Luang Namtha there are two older forms for ‘one’ *mət* and *mooc*, as well as ‘two’ *buər* in limited usage.

When using numerals with count classifiers, the native ‘one’ *mət* is used (Table 4).

Table 4: Bit ‘one’ with classifiers

<i>mət</i> ʔan	‘one thing (general)’
<i>mət</i> kon	‘one person’
<i>mət</i> kraaw	‘one moment’ > ‘just a moment’
<i>mət</i> diəw	‘one now’ > ‘just now’
<i>mət</i> nɛɛw	‘one way’ > ‘the same’

These count classifiers are almost exclusively Tai borrowings. There are some cases of use with native terms *psiiŋ mət boh* (person-one-village) ‘people of the same village’ or *ʔuuŋ ʔaac mət smpuul* (younger.sibling-older.sibling-one-stomach) ‘children of the same mother’. This is not one of the “usual” reflexes of ***muuy**/***mooy** that would be expected in Khmuic or Palaungic. Interestingly, Ksingmul has a similar word *met* found in restricted use: *tʰamet cak* (one-body) ‘just one person’ and *met ʔnɛɛn* (one-small) ‘a little bit.’

The second ‘one’ word in Bit is *mooc*. This word is used in the sense of ‘other, another’, as in *ʔvʋ mooc* (3SG.NEU-one) ‘another one, a different one’ or *koo waʔ bɔɔn mooc* (3SG.FEM-to.go-place-other) ‘she went to another place’. The word is limited to this adjectival use, but within this role it is used without any sense of being marked. This semantic expansion of ‘one’ to ‘other’ is found in the Tai languages spoken in Luang Namtha. In the Khang language, which is spoken in Vietnam and closely related to Bit, we find the word *mot* in similar usage. Despite its formal similarity to *mət*, this word seems to be the regular reflex of ***mooc**, as final -c merged with /t/ in Khang. Neither Bit nor Ksingmul have lost final -c so *mət* and *mooc* are etymologically distinct.

The old Bit *buər* ‘two’ has become a poetic echo word used with *mooc* ‘other’. For example,

<i>ʔah</i>	<i>mɛɛn</i>	<i>kee</i>	<i>mooc</i>	<i>kee</i>	<i>buər</i>
NEG	COP	3PL	other	3PL	other
‘It’s not some other group of people (that we are talking about here)’.					

This usage suggests that before the completion of the semantic transition of these words out of the realm of numerals, there was still a sense of a delexicalized counting progression, *mooc buər*. Other counting terms used with metaphorical meaning are found in borrowings from Tai, usually using the pairs *sɔɔŋ-saam* ‘two-three’ or *sip-saaw* ‘ten-twenty’ to express a sense of repetition as intensity, rather than quantity:

ɲat *sɔɔŋ* *ɲat* *saam*
to.die two to.die hree
‘to go in and out of consciousness many times’

sip *ʔeer* *saaw* *ʔeer*
ten to.beg twenty to.beg
‘to implore repeatedly’

These fossilized *mooc* ‘one’ and *buər* ‘two’ forms are not recognized by speakers of Bit as numerals, while *mət* is seen simply as singular quantifier.

5. Native numerals in Bit temporal deixis

Bit incorporates the native forms for ‘one’ and ‘two’ into the reckoning of time into past and future. The template also seems to retain old words that have become fused as the minor syllable of a disyllabic word. These systems both employ vowel mutation for a rhythm and rhyme scheme that seem to make them easier to remember.

5.1 Counting days

Bit has a complex set of temporal deictics used to reference days and years in the past and future. When counting days, Bit project +6 into the future, but only -2 into the past. The starting point in this set is ‘today’, which is the Tai borrowing *mii* ‘day’ and realized as ‘today’ with the Tai compound *mii nii* or the mixed construction *mii hee* ‘this day’. Days in the future follow the lexically transparent *mii kaʔ* or *ʔɲkaʔ* ‘tomorrow’ with terms that are formed with a prefix and suggest segmental manipulation motivated by sound play in future +2 and on. The full set is given in Table 5.

Table 5: Bit counting ‘days’

-2	<i>mii tmaan</i>	“day” + “before”
-1	<i>sɲii</i>	“yesterday”
present	<i>mii nii</i> / <i>mii hee</i>	“day” + “this” (with Tai <i>nii</i> and Bit <i>hee</i> modifiers)
+1	<i>mii kaʔ</i> / <i>ʔɲkaʔ</i>	“day” + “tomorrow”
+2	<i>clmɔɔy</i>	
+3	<i>clmiiy</i>	
+4	<i>clsiiy</i>	
+5	<i>cldeh</i>	
+6	<i>cldɔɔŋ</i>	

The FUTURE count words are marked by the /cl-/, which does not have any concrete meaning for speakers. One would hypothesize that this is a reduced form of another word that has been compounded, as with the years, below. The mutation of the rhyme -ɔɔy > iiy in +2 > +3 follows the principles of Bit sound iconism where open vowels are smaller than close vowels, a rare phenomenon described by Diffloth for Bahnar (1994). Thus /i/ is of greater intensity than /ɔ/, indicating more time from present. The next term *clsiiy*, with /s/ in the initial position of the major syllable, serves at least as a bridge to the following two that share /d/ in the initial position and differing rhymes¹⁴. When counting out the full system, people often use knuckles starting with their pinky finger and moving to their ring finger.

¹⁴ Interestingly, when asked about numerals in a short linguistic elicitation exercise with Bit speakers in Phongsaly, the informant gave the temporal deictics for +1 to +6 as numerals (Gregoire Schlemmer, personal communication). As will be discussed further below, the Bit have a narrative of loss of numbers that is part of the better-known

5.2 Counting years

The normal word for ‘year’ in Bit is the borrowed Tai form *pīi*. It is interesting to note that the set for counting years in the past and future is a balanced -3/+3 system, in contrast to the reckoning of days that is overwhelmingly oriented towards specificity in the future. The temporal deictics for ‘year’ are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Bit counting ‘years’

-3	lɿraa	
-2	lɿbii	#bii ‘three’ ?
-1	lɿmaaŋ	maaŋ ‘before’
present	pīi hee / pīi sʔee	sʔee ‘present’
+1	lɿmooc	#mooc ‘one’
+2	lɿbuər / lɿmuər	#buər ‘two’
+3	lɿbiir	

/lɿ-/ can be analyzed as the “old” word for year, as retained in Bumang and Khang *duəŋ* ‘year,’ with a predicatable d-l correspondence. For speakers of Bit, it the reduced form /lɿ/ has become lexically fused with the main element of the word. Some speakers are heard to say *pīi lɿmooc* for ‘next year’, which is etymologically redundant. Moreover, I have never heard a Bit speaker identify /lɿ/ with the meaning ‘year’. There are variations using /lɿ/: *lɿmiiŋ* ‘two years before present’ and *lɿnʔaa* [ləŋ.nəʔ.ʔa:] ‘recent years before’.

Reckoning years into the future, *mooc* ‘one; other’ and *buər* ‘two; other’ are used. This may reflect the poetic echo discussed above. Beyond this, ‘three years from present’ is *lɿbiir*, using vowel alternation to expand the template, rather than a lexical word such as a reflex of *peʔ ‘three’. It is possible that *lɿbii* ‘two years before present’ preserves this old word for ‘three’. It is possible that *lɿraa* ‘three years before present’ is related to the Palaungic word *(l)-ʔa:r ‘two’, with some segmental mutation and confusion over the original meaning.

When considering systems for counting time past and future, it is worth mentioning the 10-day cycle of days that is used by many people in the uplands to determine the timing of various social prohibitions. In Bit society, this set – *ruəŋ too kaa kaap dap rwaay miŋ plik kat kot* is almost exclusively heard in a full recital of all members. In other words, the utility of this set is maintained by the performance of a chant in which all members must be recalled in order to function. Rischel (1995) commented that although the Mlabri retained a full set of numerals, they were almost exclusively used in recitation form.

6. Specialized counting: Rhyming play and poetic (in)stability

It was not long into my fieldwork with speakers of Bit that I heard a peculiar counting system used by children when they were playing. Usually, they would count out the “numbers” as they picked up sticks or stones, competing to complete the task faster and faster. Adults know the system as well, but it is not used for any “serious” purpose. When asked to recite the play counting, adults almost universally started laughing midway and often could not complete the full set. Children, as well, tend to recite the set as quickly as possible, but slow down at the end as the last three are trickier to pronounce, seemingly emphasizing the completion of the set. Most people could not explain the origin of the system itself, and they deny that what is being recited is a set of “numbers”. There are no “meanings” to be taken from any of the elements of the system. The system is passed among children in the acts of play that are unsupervised by

areal narrative of loss of writing, so it is not strange that an informant would have produced these words in a formal elicitation situation to substitute for a perceived cultural gap in their language.

parents, and exists as a child’s domain of language use that is best understood as performance of a play ritual. There is also a separate set of counting-out rhymes that are used in specific play in which people are chosen to be “it”.

This Bit play counting system seems to have origins as a socially functional numeral system. One informant explained that this system arose in the days when they lost their writing. The association of loss of numerals with the more common motif of lost literacy is an interesting addition an important discourse on cultural contact in upland Southeast Asia. In these old days, his explanation continued, this system was used for counting large quantities of items that were being sold or traded, as markers of a group of 10. The system is now purely a play system, but we are faced with the possibility that the play set evolved out of a functional, evasive system of counting.

This set has 12 elements and is recited at normal speed until around four, at which point the chant gets faster and then starts to slow down around nine. Each element consists of a two-syllable “word”, some of which the form of canonical sesquisyllabic words. Others have not only a full vowel in the first syllable but can have a long vowel followed by a short vowel, which is atypical for Bit. The system, as recorded in Luang Namtha is presented in Table 7, together with a version of the system composed of just 10 members recorded for Buxing¹⁵ by Dao (2004) in China.

Table 7: Bit play counting system

	Luang Namtha, Laos	Nam Khaen, Yunnan, China
1	kmniŋ / kannniŋ	ka nŋ
2	kmnɔŋ / kanniŋ	ka nɔŋ
3	maypɔŋ	mai pɔŋ
4	maypeʔ	mai pik
5	ceʔreʔ / cekrek	tʃik tiŋ
6	camram	tʃum ram
7	kɔŋkuu	kɔŋ ku
8	kɔŋmɛ	kɔŋ mɛ
9	sipdɔʔ / sipdɔʔ	tʃik tɔʔ
10	ʔaayweʔ	ʔai vɛʔ
11	ʔaaywaal	
12	kwaal kweʔ / cwaal cweʔ	

As introduced above, the only native Bit numerals remaining in the language are two forms of ‘one’ and ‘two’. Of these three forms, two have assumed metaphorical meaning and are frozen in in the temporal deictics. However, we find some relics of the old numerals in the play counting system, with some phonological mutation and poetically motivated restructuring.

Looking through the twelve elements of the Bit system recorded in Luang Namtha we can propose some hypotheses. The twelve elements seem to be formed in pairs of two, with some poetic device bridging between the pairs. This interpretation is supported by the prosody used in reciting them.

The first two elements *kmniŋ kmnɔŋ* are clearly related to the Tai words for ‘one’ and ‘two’ and have a prefixed /km-/ syllable. Tai ‘one’ *niŋ*, is followed by Tai ‘two’ *ɔŋ* with the initial consonant replaced with /n/ for alliteration. The possible origin of the first syllable /km-/ can be interpreted in three ways: first, it was originally /kn-/ , a nominalizing prefix; second, it could be the Tai verb *kam* ‘to grab in the hand’, which would seem salient in light of the task of picking up small items from the ground involved in some children’s games. A third possibility is that it is related to the prefix /kn-/ or /k-/ that is used with Khmu for numerals 1-3, as discussed in Section 7.2. Some speakers pronounced /km-/ as /kn-/. It is interesting that

¹⁵ This is the Chinese rendering of the Bit word *psiŋ* ‘person’. In Laos, the word is not strictly an ethnonym, but rather a designation used as a general reference to “Self” in opposition to “Other”.

the rhyme set starts out with Tai numerals, in light of the fact that native ‘one’ and ‘two’ are the only numerals to be preserved in Bit.

The second pair *maypɔŋ maypeʔ* preserve native numerals ‘three’ and ‘four’, which can be retrieved as *peʔ* and *pɔŋ* respectively, with some interpretation. The two have been reversed, and the final of ‘four’ has been changed from /n/ to /ŋ/ in order to produce the interlinear rhyme with *kmnɔŋ*. This is cognate with Khmuic ***puən**, and confirmed by the closely related Bumang language, spoken in China, which has *pɔn* ‘four’. However, recalling the Thai Then form *pdɔŋ* ‘four’ we have independent evidence for -ŋ, which also occurs in an innovated form in that language. Three /peʔ/ is cognate with the Khmuic ***peʔ**.

The pair *ceʔreʔ camram* ‘5-6’ does not give many hints about its origin. These members do appear to take the form of stative expressives. If this is correct, the base forms would be *creʔ* / *crek* and *cram*. It seems a stretch to propose that *cram* is related in some way to the Khmer ‘five’ *pram*. It seems likely that *maypeʔ* and *ceʔreʔ* are interlinear rhymes, leaving the possibility that *camram* was in the fifth position and switched for rhyming purposes. I have recorded a few people saying *cekrek*. The Chinese Buxing data confirms the rhyming intent in *mai tʃik – tʃik tiŋ*. The second element in this pair is the only place where there is significant diversion between these two Bit versions.

The pair *kəŋkuu kəŋmɛɛ* is linked with the *kəŋ* element. Depending upon the speaker and the type of play, /ɔ/ is also heard as a long vowel. The Bit word for finger is *rŋkɔŋ*; rŋ- is a common nominalizing prefix for tools. Following this line of reasoning, /kuu/ could be the Tai word /khuu/ ‘pair’ (Bit does not have aspirated stops) and /mɛɛ/ could be ‘mother’, indicating ‘one’ and ‘two’, by way of a ‘mother’ and a ‘pair’, in reverse order. Counting by extending the thumb from a fist for ‘six’ could give **rŋkɔŋ mɛɛ* and then the index finger for ‘seven’ **rŋkɔŋ kuu*. The pair was then subsequently reversed and shifted in the order. There is no interlinear rhyming linking this pair with the previous or following pairs. This is somewhat speculative, but the principles are not far-fetched.

The pair *sipdɔʔ ʔaayweʔ* may play on the numeral ‘nine’ in two ways. First, *sipdɔʔ/sipdoʔ* could be interpreted as ‘little 10’, from the Tai *sip* ‘ten’ and the Bit *doʔ* ‘small’. Also, in a variety of Thai Then numerals recorded by Proschan (quoted in Rischel 2009) the cardinal numeral ‘nine’ is *sip*, drawing a direct parallel between the languages through this innovative form, yet complicating the social history of the play counting system with this overlap between the play and the functional. The Thai Then form could be result of bilingual play. In *ʔaayweʔ* we find the old form ‘nine’ as *ʔaay*. For the reconstructed proto-Khmuic ‘nine’ ***ka:j/ka:s** we would expect a Bit form of *kaay* or *kaas* [ka:j^h]. However, evidence from Mlabri ‘nine’ *gaʔ* suggests a voiced initial ***g**, which would be realized as /ʔ/ in contemporary Bit; so, ***ga:j^h** > ʔaay^h with loss of final aspiration in recitation mode. Strong evidence for the unvoiced initial comes from Khmu, but Rischel proposed that the attested form *kaay* could be a borrowing.

The last pair *ʔaaywaal cwaalcweʔ*, takes the system past the decimal structure. The putative element *ʔaay* ‘nine’ is followed by *waal*. This is rhymed with the first element of the last element, giving a *waal – cwaal/kwaal* transition. The reconstructed proto-Khmuic form ‘ten’ ***gal**, would give ʔal in Bit. The c-/k- initial in the last element suggests that the *waal-cwaal* could be a mutated form in which a Bit form ʔal and a different reflex of ***gal** became the object of playful mutation. Evidence from ‘ten’ in Thai Then *mkaal* and Iduh *mgoah* offers a bilabial initial sequence, which could be responsible for the rounded /u/. Again, the *weʔ* element seems to be offering ‘plus’ one. Thus an eleventh element ‘9-10’ and a twelfth element ‘10 plus one’. If the labial effect is indeed influencing the articulation of these steps, it is possible that *weʔ* is a mutated form of the old *met/mət* ‘one’. This seems feasible in a system where the order of the members are rearranged to create interlinear rhymes when needed. Another possible explanation for *weʔ* is that it is the word ‘left (side)’, with some notion of addition if one counts the primary numbers on the right hand.

If we take the last two pairs together, the progression from 9 to 12 could be

(9) small ten > (10) nine plus one > (11) nine-ten > (12) ten plus one

The proposed meaning of the last element noteworthy. Some informants did not give the (11) form, ending on (12), which as the eleventh element would indeed be ‘ten plus one’. The people who recite the numbers without (11) inevitably get caught up because the pattern of pairs is then confused.

The history of this system remains obscure. Despite the speculative nature of some of the details above, it does seem that there are fossilized remnants of the original proto-Khmuic numeral system. In the contemporary system, however, the functional element is subordinate to the sound element. The flexibility of the semantics is enhanced in a system where the numerals are replaced entirely with the borrowed Tai forms, and the “stability” of the system requires recitation of the entire set.

7. Number play in areal linguistic culture

7.1 Counting-out rhymes as game, ritual and performance

We can consider the Bit play counting system to be a type of “counting-out rhyme.” Rubin (1995) provides a useful account of these systems from the perspective of memory and orality. These rhyming schemes, solidly located in the realm of children’s play, provide a fascinating view on language transmission. In counting-out rhymes, children select people to do something, so the correct articulation and pattern of the lines is essential to the process, and therefore the shared outcome. The English counting-out rhyme *eeny meeny miney mo, catch a tiger by the toe, if he hollers let him go, eeny meeny miney mo* is the classic example.

In counting-out rhymes, nonsense lines are mingled with lines that have real meaning that communicate a coherent story. The memory and performance of these rhymes are thus a product of both the poetic and the semantic. However, it is believed that the poetic devices play a stronger role than the constraints on meaning in the reproduction of the rhymes. Moreover, poetic structure seems to contribute to the contributes the stability of these rhymes. This is supported by the fact that although there is some variation among count-out rhymes, they tend to be remarkably stable.

When Bit children play their version of hide-and-seek, they use a counting-out system with nine elements that are chanted with even stress: *cmpuk, cmpiy, pnaa, seen, sɔɔn, keew, mɛɛɲ, kɛɛɲ, mum*. The meaning of these words is unknown to the speakers, and they are clear in their explanation that this is not a counting system; it is used only for determining who is “it” in children’s games. This system is considered to be an entirely different set from the play counting that was introduced above. The first two words seem typologically to be Bit because of their disyllabic structure. The second and third elements look like Tai words that are political-military titles, but again, the Bit associate no particular meaning with them, or any other of the words. Children also chant another version of this when they play: *huə khiiŋ, huə khaa, pnaa sɔɔn seen, keew mɛɛɲ kɛɛɲ mum*. This version starts out with what appears to be the Tai words *huə khiiŋ* ‘ginger’ and *huə khaa* ‘galangal’. The overall structure is clearer, the following elements preserve common rhyming patterns. First, *pnaa sɔɔn seen* has a vowel alternation in a repeated syllable, and second, a four word construction ABCD where BC have the same rhyme. The play element of the first set is higher because the words have been detached from the poetic structures that would help preserve meaning.

7.2 Variations on play counting

Counting-out systems have been recorded in Phong (Badenoch fieldnotes 2017, 2020) and Tin (Rischel 1997), compiled in Table 8. Tin 1 and Tin 2 were recorded by among Tin speakers in

Laos, who had partial knowledge of the native Tin numeral system. He calls these systems “nursery rhyme” numerals, although he mentions that they are not numerals in the strict sense, because their function is more of play and performance, taught separately to children as part of their linguistic culture.

In Tin 2, the Lao numerals are mutated using replacement and rhyming patterns. The second element is the base, and the initial consonant is replaced. Another element is then placed before the base, using alliteration and rhyme, as well as compounding with other words to enhance the playfulness of the word. This demonstrates the deep bilingualism of the Tin people who created this system, and how that bilingualism is a part of the culture of linguistic play.

Table 8: Play counting systems in Phong and Tin

	Phong Laan 1 (Badenoch, fieldnotes 2017)	Phong Laan 2 (Badenoch, fieldnotes 2020)	Tin 1 (Rischel 1997)	Tin 2 (Rischel 1997)
1	ʔannin	muəyh	‘an nin	lin khin (<nin)
2	ʔannəŋ	mat	‘an nəŋ	ləŋ khəŋ (<səŋ)
3	kəmpəŋ / ʔəŋʔ pəŋ	siəŋ lat	‘an kəŋ	ma kham (<saam)
4	cəɛɛɛ	siəŋ ləy	kacaaw	caw pii (<sii)
5	kəmpɛɛ	ʔii təy	‘an naaw	mak waa (<haa)
6	kəmpət	ʔii taŋ	‘an nok	cap cok (<hok)
7	ksəʔ ʔət	may laŋ / ʔii mɛɛ laŋ	‘an hok	mək het (<cət)
8	krwər	may luy / ʔii mɛɛ luy	‘an hək	‘ət ‘et (<pɛɛt)
9	pəl	tuy	makək	mak paw (<kaw)
10	pləəp	kadiən	kacik	mak / may n̩ip (<sip)
11		ʔii sə		
12		tam pleəŋ		

The first Phong Laan set is used for determining who is “it” when playing hide-and-seek. The children put their hands in the center of a circle, and count off. Whoever is gets the *pləəp* is the unlucky one who has to search for the others. According to a native speaker explanation, 1-6 is the “old” part of the set, while seven to ten is “new”. This makes sense, because in contrast to the “old” words, which have no meaning for contemporary native speakers, the “new” words are transparent. The words are transparent, and underscore the playful nature of these rhymes; *ksəʔ ʔət* ‘pubic hair (male), *krwər* ‘twisted, tangled’, *pəl* ‘to throw underhand, *pləəp* ‘(expressive of) an object disappearing into a hole. The rhyme of *kəmpət* and *ʔət* connect these line. And one must assume that the *ʔət* ‘penis’ is the playful motivation for the last four elements. Thus, the semantics of the ending are: whoever gets the tangled ball of public hair tossed into their mouth is the unlucky one.

This set is the same as the Bit in 1-5, with minor variation on the basic template. It seems that four and five have been reversed, because *kəmpɛɛ* would feasibly be ‘three’. However, in Phong varieties that retain ‘three’ the vowel is /iə/ (see Phong evasive counting below). This set is also interesting because the informant who provided the data mentioned that 7-10 were newly created to complete the set.

The second Phong Laan set is also used in selecting people, but for this one the function is to eliminate one-by-one the lucky people who will not become “it”. This set starts with *muəyh* ‘housefly’ and *mat* ‘louse’. The third and fourth elements are men’s names, with the Tai *siəŋ*

‘man who has ordained’, and women’s names with the female prefix *ʔii*. The seventh and eighth elements vary with *may* or *ʔii mɛɛ*. This set was identified as the informant as being “old”, meaning that it has not been modified from the form in which it was received from his parents. The final *mɛɛ peɛŋ* is the ‘lucky person that was chosen,’ and therefore eliminated. This system utilizes pairs defined by a common first element such as *siəŋ*, *ʔii* and *may*, which seems relevant for the Bit *may-* and *kəŋ-*. The preference for euphony seems to work across semantics and etymology.

Tin 1 starts in exactly the same way as the Phong and mirrors the substitution of /n/ for /s/ in ‘two’. The paired structure shows a trend towards alliteration between the elements; n-n, k-k, n-n, h-h, and k-k. Rhyming is also an important part of the system, starting with the second member: *ɔŋ-ɔŋ*, *aaw-aaw*, *ok-ok*, *ɔ-ɔk*, but excluding the last.

Tin 2 is an entirely Tai-based system that uses mutation of segments to “hide” the original Tai numeral. For the first and second members only, the first and second elements are differentiated only by the initial consonant. From the third member on, the words are produced by replacing the first consonant of the Tai numeral and adding another syllable in front to form an unrelated Tai compound, or nonce words. So far, the system does not seem to be borrowed wholesale from Tai, but is rather the product of Mal-Pray bilingual creativity.

Dai (2012) recorded a Khmu counting system in China that seems to be a transitional system (Table 9). The numerals 1-3 are preserved, with presyllables that are found in some Khmu varieties in Laos as well. However, from 4 on the system switches to some type of play. The third member is a bridging word, tied to the 1-2 by the *kən-/kə-* presyllable, then initiating a rhyming sequence, with the near rhyme *-eʔ / -et*, followed by a rhymed *-el*.

Table 9: Khmu transitional numeral system

	Khmu (Dai 2012)
0	və
1	kən mo:i
2	kə ba:r
3	kə peʔ
4	nam ʔet
5	nam ʔel
6	tɛil del
7	nam vət
8	m pə:t
9	sə vət
10	si ver

The last two members share the minor syllable *sə-/si-* as well as *v-* alliteration. Additional fieldwork is needed to deepen the analysis of this rhyming system. Dai commented that these were not commonly used, with the exception of 1-3 in their forms without the *k-* presyllable, suggesting some sort of specialized or play function.

7.3 Phong evasive counting systems

Peculiar counting systems have been noted by Rischel (2009) in Thin and Diffloth (personal communications) in Phong. Rischel considered these to be “complex” numeral expressions, meaning that they include “ordinary” numerals, borrowings from Thai and remaining ones that are “particularly interesting”. Rischel proposed that these systems were composed of “all-purpose” and “special purpose” numerals.

These seem to be particularly common among the Phong and Tin peoples of Laos. These have been discussed briefly in Tappe and Badenoch (2021), and seem to have their origins in the market exchange between Phong and speakers of Tai after the Khmuic numeral system was being lost. Data for Phong and Tin are shown in Table 10 (preserving original notation).

Table 10: Phong evasive counting systems

	Tin Sakad (Rischel 2009)	Ban Saleuy (Tappe and Badenoch 2021)	Diffloth (Diffloth pc.)	Phaen (Badenoch fieldnotes 2017)
1	mɔːjleʔ	baʔan	boʔan	baʔan
2	piar	baarʔan	baarʔan	baarʔan
3	pheʔ	piəʔan	piəʔan	piəʔan
4	phoːn	ksuut / bəksuut	phon	ksuut
5	phiathiː	bəbiəŋ tiəy	buaŋ tuay	bobiəŋ
6	phiapheʔ	bətiəy plaay baʔan	boʔ pʔua	tɪim baniiw
7	ced	ʒiet	giat	tɪim baar niiw
8	phiaphoːn	bətɛk	tit	tɪim piə niiw
9	kao	phrom	prom	prom
10	mɛʔleʔ	baar biəŋ tiəy	buʔvuur	baar biəŋ

Phong uses bilingual plays on words to form several of these evasive numerals. For example, *ksuut* ‘four’ means ‘poking iron’, playing on the fact that the Phong pronunciation of Tai ‘four’ and ‘poking iron’ are the same *leek sii*. Similarly, *phrom* ‘nine’ is a playful recognition of homophony in the Phong pronunciation of the Tai words for ‘nine’ and ‘old’. In Tai these are differentiated only by tone. Finally, *boʔ pʔua* is a play on the Tai word ‘six’ and ‘bamboo sp.’, both of which are produced as *hok* without the tonal distinction; *pʔua* is the Phong term for that type of bamboo.

More straightforward approaches include the use of ‘side’ and ‘finger’, as seen in the Phaen’s ‘5’ *bobiəŋ* ‘one side’, that is the five fingers of a hand on one side. This is followed by forms created from *tɪim* ‘to add’ a number of ‘fingers’ *niiw*. Thus ‘six’, ‘seven’ and ‘eight’ use *tɪim* with the recycled native numerals 1-3 and the Tai borrowing *niiw*. Saleuy ‘five’ *bəbiəŋ tiəy* is ‘one.side-hand’ and ‘six’ *bətiəy plaay baʔan* is ‘one.hand-to.exceed-one.thing’, where *plaay* is a borrowed Tai term that retains the original cluster /pl/ that was lost in the local Tai varieties.

In this way, the Phong evasive numerals use playful strategies enabled by homophony and semantic juxtaposition across languages, as well as combinations of native and borrowed terms.

7.4 Ksingmul temporal deictics and sound play

The Ksingmul temporal deictics system shows compensation for what is perceived to be an incomplete system through sound play. This may be related to the Bit forms discussed above, demonstrating an intersection between the functional and the poetic. The Ksingmul system allows for counting forward and backward in time +/- 5 days (Table 11). Interestingly, specification of present/past is done externally to these forms.

Table 11: Ksingmul temporal deictics, counting days (Badenoch fieldnotes 2015)

+/-1	phoo biər
+/-2	phoo pɛɛ
+/-3	phoo poon
+/-4	phoo piin
+/-5	phoo paan

The native Ksingmul words *biər* ‘two’, *pɛɛ* ‘three’ and *poon* ‘four’ are followed by forms *piin* and *paan*, which are not lexical words, but created through mutation of the vowel as part of a play sequence. When discussing the ordinary numerals, people confidently give 1-3 as native, and from ‘four’ on it becomes a joking matter, as *piin* and *paan* are re-incorporated from the

deictics as ‘five’ and ‘six’. When asked about forms for ‘seven’ and ‘eight’ people try out various vowels, but here we are solidly in the realm of play as the Ksingmul vowel space is limited and there is great variation among speakers, if they chose to entertain the idea of lexical productivity in this semantic realm. One speaker I recorded produced *mooy biər pɛɛ poon piin paan pit pat pɔɔt pəət*, a “full” set of ten. He produced this same set on several occasions. Others gave similar series with slight differences in the details of the rhyme in the higher members. This exercise inevitably ends in laughter. It should be noted that the Palaungic form ‘six’ *phan* (see Lamet in Table 2 above) could be the source of +5, which would mean that the play involves one form with a mutated vowel and a switch in the order, motivated by the string of alliteration starting with +2 and the temporal prefix *phoo*. Ksingmul has been considered to be Khmuic, so the possibility of a Palaungic cognate numeral is interesting. The explanation could be a simple matter of playfully maximizing contrasts within the vowel space: oo > ii > aa > i > a > ɔɔ > əə.

For the time being, we are faced with the question of play or inheritance – in this case, the play option is not too fanciful. This type of vowel mutation is an integral part of Ksingmul reduplication, but because of these playful vowel alternation many people I spoken with are not sure if *phoon* is a “real” numeral. The Ksingmul temporal deictics, although limited, do demonstrate the tendency for playing with sounds in order to extend patterns of progression, as well as the interaction between “normal” counting, specialized numeration and play.

7.5 Tai play codes as external motivation

In the Tin 2 play system above, the first and second elements draw on a play mutation pattern. This may have links to a broader play practice found in Tai languages. In Muang Hiem, Houaphan, there are play codes known as *kham phɔɔŋ*, in which consonant and vowel manipulation are used together with reduplication. For example, the following sentence given by a speaker of Tai Daeng

<i>vaa</i>	<i>cii</i>	<i>pay</i>	<i>kin</i>	<i>khaw</i>	<i>nam</i>
to.say	IRR	to.go	to.eat	rice	together
I was thinking I would go eat together [with someone].					

is rendered as

laavɛɛ liiceɛ laypɛɛ linkeɛm lawkheɛm lamnɛɛm

In this rhyming code, which seems to be shared by many Tai languages, disyllabic words are created by adding /l/ to the front of the word, copying the original rhyme forward to complete the first syllable and then replacing the vowel of the second syllable with /ɛɛ/ or /ɛɛm/:

laavɛɛ < laavaa < lvaa < vaa

and

linkeɛm < linkin < lkin < kin.

There are many variations on this type of play, including a reduplication and replacement with interplay between /l/ and /kh/. Considering the T’ in 2 forms, this type of play code could explain *liŋ khiiŋ* ‘one’ and *lɔɔŋ khɔɔŋ* ‘two’, where

liŋ khiiŋ < liŋ niŋ < lniŋ < niŋ ‘one’

and

lɔɔŋ khɔɔŋ < lɔɔŋ sɔɔŋ < lɔɔŋ < sɔɔŋ ‘two’

This only explains two of the members of that set, and the system seems to be a combination of different devices. So far, it does not seem that the system has been borrowed wholesale from a Tai group, and the presence of the many templates for playfully obscuring meaning in Tai may have been involved playful innovation across ethnolinguistic groups.

8. Rhyme over reason: Sound, meaning and play in counting systems

In the uplands of Northern Laos, one finds several types of “play” counting systems in the Austroasiatic languages spoken there. These include game-type play, as well as a more theoretical play, in which the rules of sound and meaning are manipulated for some social purpose. Counting-out systems used by children in games show variation even within languages. There is also a tendency to create evasive counting systems that may have originated in the need to mask discussions in economic transactions. From the data presented here, it seems that this might be part of a process of losing native numerals and adopting Tai forms. While the evasive systems had (they are generally not in “serious” use anymore) clear social function, it was the use of various reduplication and rhyming, often across languages, that drove the creation of these forms.

There is significant cross-over between these types of counting systems. Despite the geographic and linguistic distance between Bit, Phong and Tin, the existence of play counting systems that share the basic forms of the Bit *kmniŋ-kmnɔɔŋ* is remarkable. Moreover, it seems that this Bit system that was at least partially functional in the past, has come to occupy a purely playful position in the linguistic culture of its speakers. This paper has tried to explore historical clues to explain the forms, because these are play systems, there is no way to know most of what has been done with these words. They do, however, make an interesting contribution to our knowledge of the linguistic culture of specific groups while providing glimpses of larger areal phenomena.

The existence of these systems is needless to say not limited to northern Laos. They have been recorded across the Austroasiatic family, linguistically and geographically, from Munda to Aslian. In many cases, it seems that the forces of rhyme dominate the limitations of reason. The influence of other languages on the internal creativity of speakers of these languages is also evident, in this paper it was the Tai languages of the region; in the case of Munda, there is Indo-Aryan influence, while in the Aslian languages spoken in Malaysia we are not surprised to find Malay.

The study of these play systems is an important complement to the reconstruction of proto numeral systems. Focus on how these play systems intersect with the “serious” numerals in multilingual settings, brings to the forefront the desire to have language that is aesthetically pleasing, reinforcing of social differentiation and ambiguous in terms of functional communication.

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